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Environmental Diplomacy in the Light of International Convergence: an Effective Approach towards International Interaction and Sustainable Peace

Abstract:

Today, environmental protection and sustainable development are two fundamental pillars of human existence. In this process, the major roles are played by governments and international organizations. Adherence to international obligations (erga Omnes) and Jus Cogens are two important rudiments in environmental diplomacy towards sustainable development. Surely sustainability in development and Environmental protection won't be happened without serious regional interactions and international cooperation. Also sustainable development and development sustainability are not on their accurate path except international interactions and global peace. Along that, environmental diplomacy is known as an effective method to natural resources and ecosystems conservation. So, environmental discussions are very much important international convergence reason. Therefore, international community can lead to global environmental conservation strategies with that convergence attitude. This research aims to determine the international environmental law evolution firstly and government's roles in front of environmental challenges lying international convergence and legal fundamentals. So, environmental threats and hazards, display an illogical human act, that can be solved under the shadow of international convergence and moving to environmental conservation and global peace.

Keywords: environmental Diplomacy, environmental protection, common obligations and international convergence, international environmental law, sustainable development, international responsibility

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